

Optical properties of Dy_xTi_{1-x}O₂ nanocomposites

J. Dhanalakshmi*^a and D. Pathinettam Padiyan^a

^aDepartment of Physics, Manonmaniam Sundaranar University, Tirunelveli-627012

Tamil Nadu, India.

*dhanam0610@gmail.com

Abstract

Dy_xTi_{1-x}O₂ nanocomposites with X=0-0.1 are obtained through sol-gel method. The prepared sample is annealed at 450 °C for 2 h and characterized using DRS and PL spectra. The absorbance spectra of Dy_xTi_{1-x}O₂ nanocomposites, compared to pure titania, show red shift in the band-gap transition which can be attributed to the charge-transfer transition between Dy³⁺ ion f electrons and the TiO₂ conduction or valence band. The absorption hump seen at 701 nm reveals the visible-light absorbability of these nanocomposites. This peak is attributed to the 4f electron transitions of Dy³⁺ ions. The tauc plot gives indirect band gap of Dy_xTi_{1-x}O₂ nanocomposites and are 3.212(1), 3.187(1), 3.157(2), 3.143(1) and 3.142(1) for x=0.02, 0.04, 0.06, 0.08 and 0.10 respectively. It has been observed that the band gap decreases with the increase in Dy inclusion. From PL spectra several emission bands are observed including violet emissions at 422 & 434 nm, blue emission at 447 nm, blue-green emission 485 nm and green emission 531 nm were observed. These emissions are assigned to the surface state emissions and due to the recombination of trapped electron-hole arising from dangling bonds in the TiO₂ nanoparticles. With the increase of Dy concentration, intensity of the PL emission has decreased as in Figure 4.8. The decrease in the PL intensity ensures the separation of charge carriers. This clearly indicates that these Dy_xTi_{1-x}O₂ nanocomposites have a better light-absorbing ability than bare TiO₂ since it absorb the visible light, which makes them a potential visible light photocatalyst.

Keywords: nanocomposites; optical properties; 4f transition